

Original Article

Publication History:

Published 21/12/2020

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4392745

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Ali Haider Raza, Aziz Bhatti Shaheed Teaching Hospital, Gujrat
thunder_keeper@hotmail.com

Cite this article as:

Javed NUS, Naveed M, Raza AH. Prevalence of different disabilities among outdoor patients. Int. J. Med. Dent. Allied Health Sci. 2020;2(12). 602-606

© Copyright 2020

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License CC-BY 4.0., which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

**PREVALENCE OF DIFFERENT
DISABILITIES AMONG OUTDOOR
PATIENTS**

AUTHORS:

1. DR. NAJAM-UL-SEHAR JAVED, DHQ HOSPITAL JHELUM
2. DR. MARYUM NAVEED, BHU 148 6R HAROONABAD
3. DR. ALI HAIDER RAZA, AZIZ BHATTI SHAHEED TEACHING HOSPITAL, GUJRAT

ABSTRACT:

A disability is any condition that makes it more difficult for a person to do certain activities or interact with the world around them. These conditions, or impairments, may be cognitive, developmental, intellectual, mental, physical, sensory, or a combination of multiple factors. Impairments causing disability may be present from birth or occur during a person's lifetime. This cross-sectional study was conducted among patients presenting in outdoor departments of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, presence along with its type or absence of any kind of disability were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. There were 70 patients included in this study. There were 35 males (50%) and 35 females (40%). The mean age of the patients was 30.19±5.23 years. Out of 70 patients, only 13 had different kind of disabilities i.e., using wheel chair, deafness, blindness, amputated hands etc.

KEYWORDS: DISABILITIES

INTRODUCTION:

A disability is any condition that makes it more difficult for a person to do certain activities or interact with the world around them. These conditions, or impairments, may be cognitive, developmental, intellectual, mental, physical, sensory, or a combination of multiple factors. Impairments causing disability may be present from birth or occur during a person's lifetime. The World Health Organization proposes the following definition of disabilities "Disabilities is an umbrella term, covering impairments, activity limitations, and participation restrictions. An impairment is a problem in body function or structure; an activity limitation is a difficulty encountered by an individual in executing a task or action; while a participation restriction is a problem experienced by an individual in involvement in life situations. Disability is thus not just a health problem. It is a complex phenomenon, reflecting the interaction between features of

a person's body and features of the society in which he or she lives."

There are many different causes of disability that often affect basic activities of daily living, such as eating, dressing, transferring, and maintaining personal hygiene; or advanced activities of daily living such as shopping, food preparation, driving, or working.

For the purposes of the Americans with Disabilities Act of 1990, the US Equal Employment Opportunity Commission regulations provide a list of conditions that should easily be concluded to be disabilities: deafness, blindness, an intellectual disability, partially or completely missing limbs or mobility impairments requiring the use of a wheelchair, autism, cancer, cerebral palsy, diabetes, epilepsy, HIV/AIDS, multiple sclerosis, muscular dystrophy, major depressive disorder, bipolar disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder, obsessive compulsive disorder, and schizophrenia.

This is not an exhaustive list and many injuries and medical problems cause disability. Some

causes of disability, such as injuries, may resolve over time and are considered temporary disabilities. An acquired disability is the result of impairments that occur suddenly or chronically during the lifespan, as opposed to being born with the impairment. Invisible disabilities may not be obviously noticeable (1-3). The objective of this study was to see the prevalence of different kind of disabilities among outdoor patients.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among patients presenting in outdoor departments of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, presence along with its type or absence of any kind of disability were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

There were 70 patients included in this study. There were 35 males (50%) and 35 females (40%). The mean age of the patients was 30.19 ± 5.23 years. Out of 70 patients, only 13 had different kind of disabilities i.e., using wheel chair, deafness, blindness, amputated hands etc.

DISCUSSION:

Estimates of worldwide and country-wide numbers of individuals with disabilities are problematic. The varying approaches taken to defining disability notwithstanding, demographers agree that the world population of individuals with disabilities is very large. For example, in 2012, the World Health Organization estimated a world population of 6.5 billion people. Of those, nearly 650 million people, or 10%, were estimated to be moderately or severely disabled. In 2018 the International Labour Organization estimated that about a billion people, one-seventh of the world population, had disabilities,

80% of them in developing countries, and 80% of working age. Excluding disabled people from the workforce was reckoned to cost up to 7% of gross domestic product. There is a global correlation between disability and poverty, produced by a variety of factors. Poverty and disability go hand in hand. The poverty rate for working-age people with disabilities is nearly two and a half times higher than that for people without disabilities. Disability and poverty may form a vicious circle, in which physical barriers and stigma of disability make it more difficult to get income, which in turn diminishes access to health care and other necessities for a healthy life. In societies without state funded health and social services, living with a disability could require spending on medication and frequent health care visits, in-home personal assistance, and adaptive devices and clothing, along with the usual costs of living. The World report on disability indicates that half of all disabled people cannot afford health care, compared to a third of

abled people. In countries without public services for adults with disabilities, their families may be impoverished (4-6).

REFERENCES:

1. "Economic Model of Disability". Michigan Disability Rights Coalition. Retrieved August 11, 2012.
2. Smith, T.B. (2012). A New and Emerging Model of Disability: The Consumer Model. White Paper. The Pennsylvania State University
3. Aichner, T. & Shaltoni, A.M. (2018). "Marketing of specialised products and services to consumers with disabilities: exploring the role of advertising, country-of-origin, and e-commerce". *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*. 28 (2): 115–36. doi:10.1080/09593969.2017.1364658. S2CID 169024657.
4. Weiner, B.; Perry, R.P. & Magnusson, J. (1988). "An attributional analysis of reactions to stigmas". *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*. 55 (5): 738–

48. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.55.5.738. PMID 2974883.
5. Lerner, M.J. (1980). The belief in a just world: A fundamental delusion. New York: Plenum Press.
6. Reeve, Donna (2004). "Psycho-emotional dimensions of disability and the social model" (PDF). In Barnes, Colin; Mercer, Geof (eds.). Reeve Chapter 2004. Leeds, UK: The Disability Press. pp. 83–100. ISBN 978-0-9528450-8-9.